

SPOT TEST FOR IRON BY SUBSTITUTED VIOLURIC ACIDS

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Ferrous salts form deep blue complexes with numerous isonitroso compounds. Although the reactions are extremely sensitive, these have rarely been used in analytical practice. Krohnke (*Ber.*, 1927, **60B**, 527; *Gas-wasserfach*, 1927, **70**, 510) used a chloroform solution of isonitrosoacetophenone to detect as small as 0.03 mg. of iron per litre. Kuster (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, **155**, 157) found that a 0.0075% solution of ferrous sulphate showed a distinct reaction with isonitrosoacetylacetone. Dubsky and Kuras (*Chem. Listy*, 1929, **23**, 496) have used diisonitroacetone for testing iron in the ferrous state.

During the course of investigations on the inner-complex salts of substituted violuric acids, the author (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, **23A**, 330; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, **15B**, 245; this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 198) found that all of them developed intense blue colour with iron in the ferrous state. Thiovioluric acids are better suited for this purpose because of their complexes being deeper in colour. Diphenyl-di-*o*-tolyl- and -di-*p*-tolyl-thiovioluric acids have been used for performing spot tests for iron.

Procedure.—A drop of a ferrous salt of iron is placed on a filter paper (Whatman No. 1) or a spot plate, followed by a drop of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH about 4.5). On adding a drop of an acetone solution of one of the violuric acids (0.5%), a deep blue colour is formed. To ensure the presence of iron in the ferrous state, the solution is first reduced with a small quantity of hydroquinone before addition of the reagent solution. An excess of hydroquinone does not interfere with the colour reaction.

Sensitivity.—This test can be used to detect as little as 0.1 γ iron on paper and 0.05 γ iron on a spot plate.

Dilution limit: 1:500,000 (on paper) and 1:1,000,000 (on a spot plate).

Effect of pH.—pH has a marked effect on the formation of the blue complex of iron (II) and must be within 3.1 and 6.0. pH adjustment can be done by addition of a drop of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer.

Effect of cations and anions.—None of the common anions, such as, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, nitrite, sulphate and thiocyanate or any of the common cations, were found to interfere in the detection of iron. Although complexes are formed with most other cations, but these do not interfere provided that their concentration does not exceed one part in 100,000. None of the common cations develop any appreciable colour at such high dilutions even though their relative proportions be 10 times that of iron. Iron, however, can be conveniently tested under these conditions. It has been found that oxalate, tartrate, citrate and cyanide ions interfere with colour development and should be absent.